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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to describe students' abilities in solving real life problems. This type of research is qualitative with design studies case. subject study is student class V SD No. 1 Bhaktiseraga. Data about ability student in solve problem mathematica life real collected with test description and interview. Furthermore data analyzed with use statistics descriptive. The research procedures were: (1) giving a mathematical test in the form of a description related to arithmetic operations, (2) each student question was asked to provide an answer related to the formulation of the situation model, mathematical model, solving and interpretation of the results, (3) analyzing student answers from the point of view of ability formulation of situation models, mathematical models, solving and interpretation of results, and (4) selecting 2 students with low abilities, 2 students with moderate abilities, and 2 students with high abilities to be interviewed in an effort to verify student results. The results of this study were that the students' abilities in modeling situations were classified as very poor, while students' abilities in making mathematical models, solving and interpreting were classified as not good. Errors made by students tended to be in modeling situations. Students do not understand the description of problems related to real life. Errors in making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting are caused by students not understanding the problem or not being able to construct a situation model.

Keywords: situation model, mathematical model, problem solving, interpretation of results, real life problems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge world real about context problem or situation problem which involvement is very necessary to see aspects of the problem included in mathematical modeling, interpreting the results into the original problem (Suharta and Suarjana, 2006; 2007). Real life problem solving by students not only give chance to student for do process language, process mathematics, and reasoning about situations, but also provides opportunities to students to think critically to relate problems or their answers to situations or condition real in everyday life.

The research results of Suharta (2016) show that in problem solving mathematics life real there is trend student ignore consideration appropriate real life. Many students understand and answer math problems real life without consideration of factual relationships between real world situations and math operations. Suharta and Parwati (2020) found that student ability in giving real answers with realistic reasons classified as lacking. Seen from gender, that male students better than women at giving reason realistic. In studies the, ability student in real problem solving based only on the procedure and results shown by students. This result has a weakness because it does not describe ability students according to the stages in solving real problems.

According to Gilbert Greefrath and katrin Vorhölter (2016) steps solving problem life real consists of: a situation model, mathematical model, problem solving, as well as interpretation of the results in the form of a real situation..Assessing students' ability to each stage solving problem real important done, so that action carried out in an effort to increase the ability to solve real problems becomes more appropriate. Problem study in matter this is how description ability student in solve problem life real based on the formulation of situation models, mathematical models, problem solving, and interpretation of results.

The processes that take place in schools must always be linked to processes that exist in real life. In this regard, Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen (2000; Suharta & Suarjana, 2006) said that, by relating mathematics to the real world, students can apply the mathematics they learn in class to the real world. By relating mathematics to other disciplines, students can see that many things depend on mathematics. One way to get students interested in the mathematics being taught is by involving real life in the learning process in class.

Many mathematical concepts are extracted from real life and these concepts are developed so that they can be used to solve real problems. According to Novotna (2000) there are five reasons for solving real life problems or story problems in mathematics learning, namely: formative reasons, critical competency reasons, reasons for benefits, reasons for the characteristics of mathematics, reasons for introducing mathematics.

Thus, the function of real life problems in learning mathematics is very important, namely so that children can see the benefits of mathematics in real life and in other fields, develop reasoning, and improve students' attitudes. Apart from that, real life problems can be used as a source of inspiration for forming and constructing mathematical concepts or developing mathematical concepts.

A mathematical problem is a problem if you don't have an idea of the solution and want to solve it. Problem solving means looking for an action to achieve a goal. Problem solving involves organizing knowledge, previous experience, intuition, attitudes, beliefs and cognitive abilities (Mi Kyung Cho, Min Kyeong Kim. 2020). Not all math problems are a problem. A problem whose solution procedure is known to students is a routine problem or not a problem. A problem is a problem (non-routine problem) if the solution procedure is not yet known, and there is an interest in solving it (Megan Che, Elaine Wiegert, Karen Threlkeld..2012). Real life mathematical problems are mathematical problems in the form of stories with a real life context, and their solutions require arguments or considerations based on real life.

According to Gilbert Greefrath and Katrin Vorhölter (2016) the process of solving real life problems is as shown in the following picture.

Picture 03. Solving problem

The steps in solving story problems consist of: constructing a situation model, compiling a mathematical model, solving the problem, as well as interpretation of the results in the form of real situations. Therefore, real life considerations are very important in solving real mathematical problems, namely in making models of problem situations and mathematical modeling and in interpreting the results that have been obtained.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is qualitative with a case study design. The research subjects were fifth grade students at SD No. 1 Bhaktiserga Singaraja. Data collection techniques using tests and interviews. The mathematics test takes the form of a description relating to the concept of arithmetic operations. Problems example :

A farmer has 130 ducks placed in several cages. If each duck house can hold a maximum of 40 ducks, how many cages are needed?

For each question, students are asked to provide answers related to the formulation of situation models, mathematical models, solutions, and interpretation of results.

The research procedure is as follows.

- 1) Provide a mathematics test in the form of a description relating to arithmetic operations. The mathematics test consists of 3 questions.
- 2) For each question, students are asked to provide answers related to the formulation of situation models, mathematical models, solutions, and interpretation of results
- 3) Analyze students' answers in terms of their ability to formulate situation models, mathematical models, solutions and interpret results
- 4) Describe the mistakes made by students
- 5) Selecting 2 low-ability students, 2 medium-ability students, and 2 high-ability students to be interviewed in an effort to verify student results.

Next, the data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Students' problem-solving abilities are classified into very good, good, sufficient, not good, not very good, with conversion guidelines using absolute norms as follows.

If $X \geq 85\%$ then very good

If $70\% \leq X < 85\%$ then good

If $55\% \leq X < 70\%$ then sufficient

If $42\% \leq X < 55\%$ then it is not good

If $X < 42\%$ then it is very not good

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Research Results

Based on the answers given by students, the following identified students' abilities in solving problems and mistakes made by students.

Table 3.1. Problem solving skill

Question	Problem solving skill			
	Situation model	Mathematical Models	Solving	Interpretation
1. A farmer has 130 ducks placed in several cages. If each duck house can hold a maximum of 40 ducks, how many cages are needed?	36.56%	36.56%	36.56%	36.56%
2. The distance from Edo's house to school is 2,500 m. The distance from Siti's house to school is 4,740 m. How many meters apart are Siti's and Edo's houses?	27.27%	59.09%	59.09%	59.09%
3. Agus, a fifth grade elementary school student, had his house flooded. His 25 friends feel sorry for Agus. All of Agus's friends donated to Agus. How	54.55%	54.55%	54.55%	54.55%

many donations did Agus receive?				
Average	39.46%	50.07%	50.07%	50.07%

Question Problem solving skill

Situation model Mathematical Models Solving Interpretation

1. A farmer has 130 ducks placed in several cages. If each duck house can hold a maximum of 40 ducks, how many cages are needed? 36.56% 36.56% 36.56% 36.56%
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- Average 39.46% 50.07% 50.07% 50.07%

Based on the conversion guidelines described in the previous chapter, in general the ability of students to model situations is classified as very not good, while students' abilities in making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting are classified as not good. In detail, for the first problem, students' abilities in making situation model, the ability to make mathematical models, solving, and interpretation each of 36.56%, means that it is classified as very not good. The second problem is that students' ability to create situation models is 27.27% which is classified as very not good. The ability to create mathematical models, solving and interpreting each of 50.09% is classified as not good. the first problem is the ability of students to make models of situations, the ability to make mathematical models, solving, and interpretation each of 36.56%, classified as very not good. The third problem, the ability of students to make models of situations, make mathematical models, solving, and interpretation of 54.55% each is classified as not good.

In detail, for the first problem, students' errors in modeling situations, making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each were 63.64%, meaning that they were sufficient. The second problem, student errors in creating situation models of 72.73% are relatively high. Students' errors in making mathematical models, solving and interpreting each amounted to 40.91% which was classified as very not good. The third problem, student errors in modeling situations, making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each of 45.45%, means that it is sufficient.

Of the 14 people who experienced situation model errors, there were 8 people who made situation models by adding. Determine the number of cages needed by adding them up. $90 + 40 = 130$ means that if only 40 animals enter the cage then the number that has not entered the cage is 90. The following is an example of student answers.

1. Seorang peternak mempunyai 130 ekor itik yang ditempatkan dalam beberapa kandang. Jika masing-masing kandang itik paling banyak bisa memuat 40 ekor itik, berapa kandang yang diperlukan?

a. Model situasi : Banyaknya itik dalam kandang dikelor dihitung dengan dibagi penjumlahan

b. Model Matematika : jika hanya 40 ekor yang masuk kandang maka sisa 90 ekor yang belum masuk kandang, jadi kurang 90 kandang

c. Pemecahan : $90 + 40 = \dots$

$$\begin{array}{r} 90 \\ 40 \\ \hline 130 \end{array} +$$

1. A farmer has 130 ducks placed in several cages. If each duck house can hold a maximum of 40 ducks, how many cages are needed?

a. Situation model : The number of ducks in a cage of 40 is calculated by addition

b. Mathematics model : If only 40 birds enter the cage then there are 90 remaining that have not entered the cage. So less than 90 cages

c. Solution : $90 + 40 = \dots$

$$\begin{array}{r} 90 \\ 40 \\ \hline 130 \end{array} +$$

Figure : 4a Student Answers with Addition

The results of interviews with students who experienced the situation model error (S8), students could not state what was known and asked in the questions. However, after being directed, students can determine what is known and asked in the question, such as the following interview transcript.

R: What do you know in the problem?

S8 : He..he...he..

R: come on, just say it, whatever your answer is, it doesn't matter...

S8:(silence)

R: How many ducks are there?

S8 : 130

R: How many ducks are in 1 cage?

S8 : 40 ducks.

R: what is asked in the question?

S8 : the number of cages...

Some students use a situation model with division. The total number of ducks is divided by the number of ducks in 1 cage to produce 3 residues of 10, as follows.

1. Seorang peternak mempunyai 130 ekor itik yang ditempatkan dalam beberapa kandang. Jika masing-masing kandang itik paling banyak bisa memuat 40 ekor itik, berapa kandang yang diperlukan?

a. Model situasi : Banyak, kanda itik dihitung dengan pembagian ~~partisi~~ pembagian

b. Model Matematika : ~~130 ekor~~ ~~130~~ ~~40~~ $130 \div 40$

c. Pemecahan : $130 \div 40 = 3$ sisa 10

1. A farmer has 130 ducks placed in several cages. If each duck house can hold a maximum of 40 ducks, how many cages are needed?

- a. Situation model : the number of duck cages is calculated by division
 b. Mathematics model : $130 : 40$
 c. Solution :
 $130 : 40 = 3$ sisa 10

Figure 4b: Student Answers with Distribution

The results of interviews with subjects who did not experience errors are as follows.

R: Son...what do you know in the question?

S5: ducks...um...hey, there are lots of ducks in the cage.

R: How many ducks are in one cage?

S5 : forty

R: How many ducks are there in three cages?

S5 : add up..... forty plus forty plus forty is one hundred twenty (his hand while writing $40 + 40 + 40 = 120$)

R: How many ducks in all?

S5 : one hundred and thirty

R: How many ducks haven't got a cage yet?

S5: one cage contains ten ducks

R: How many cages do you need?

S5 : four

Based on the transcript of the interview, students who answered correctly did show a good understanding of the problem situation, making mathematical models, solving and interpreting.

Regarding student errors in mathematical modeling, in general students cannot translate real life problems into mathematical sentences. Likewise in solving and interpreting. In making mathematical modeling, students rewrite what is known in the problem.

3.2 Discussion

Mathematics is close to human life. Various human activities in everyday life use mathematics. Many real-life problems require mathematical solutions. Based on the research results as previously described, for questions number 1, 2, and 3 student errors in the model situation were 63.64%, 72.73%, 45.45% respectively, in mathematical modeling were 63.64% successively, 72.73%, 45.45%, in solving successively 63.64%, 72.73%, 45.45%, and in interpreting the results successively 63.64%, 72.73%, 45.45 %.

The first problem relates to the concept of residual division. The student's mistake in making the situation model is that the student does not write down or state the real picture that exists or is needed in the problem in accordance with real life or cannot see the problem situation model. The implication is that students cannot make mathematical models. The second problem relates to the concept of addition or subtraction arithmetic operations. This problem is addition if the position of Edo and Siti's house is opposite the school, while subtracting if the position of Edo and Siti's house is in the same direction and not opposite the school. The dominant student error cannot model the situation. Students cannot describe the real state of the problem. Errors in mathematical modeling, solving and interpretation because students do not understand the problem situation. The third problem relates to the concept of multiplication. This situation requires children to think critically in the form of adding information on the amount of donations given by each child. Student errors in modeling situations because students cannot provide additional information. Students cannot see the aspects that are in the problem. After students were given instructions that students were free to determine the amount of donation, then there were 55% of students understood and could determine situation models, mathematical models, solving, and interpreting.

The situation model is a simplification of existing problems or a mathematical description of real life problems. Situation modeling requires knowledge of the aspects of the problem such as what is known, what is being asked, and additional information needed. Student errors in making a situation model because students cannot see the aspects of the problem, the context of the problem and cannot provide the additional information needed. This supports the results of research by Suharta and Suarjana (2006; 2007) which states that real-world knowledge about the context of the problem or problem situation involved is needed to see aspects of the problem including in mathematical modeling, interpreting the results into the original problem.

Problem solving requires conceptual knowledge, procedural and the relationship between conceptual and procedural. Student errors in problem solving because students are wrong in modeling situations. In addition, there is a tendency for students to only see the numbers in the problem. This supports the results of Suharta's research (2016) that in solving real-life math problems there is a tendency for students to ignore appropriate real-life considerations. Many students understand and answer real-life math problems without considering factual relationships between real-world situations and mathematical operations.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Mathematical problems whose context is related to real life are called real life mathematical problems. The process of solving real life problems consists of four steps, namely creating a situation model, mathematical model, solving, and interpreting. The situation model is intended as a description of the problem associated with real life or additional information to the problem to match real life. Mathematical modeling is the mental process of changing a situation model into a mathematical sentence. Problem solving is the mental process of finding answers using conceptual and procedural knowledge. The intended interpretation is to relate the answers to problems in the context of everyday problems so that they become more realistic or alternative answers are given so that the evaluation is carried out more effectively and efficiently. Solving problems carried out by students needs to be studied in order to find out the mistakes made by students, giving consideration realistic in efforts to develop problem solving. Based on the research results, it can be concluded as follows.

1) Students' ability to model situations is classified as very not good, while students' abilities in making mathematical models, solving and interpreting are not good. - respectively 36.56%, meaning it is classified as very not good. The second problem is that students' ability to create situation models is 27.27% which is classified as very not good. The ability to create mathematical models, solving and interpreting each of 50.09% is classified as not good. the first problem is the ability of students to make models of situations, the ability to make mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each is 36.56%, which means that it is classified as very not good. The third problem, the ability of students to make models of situations, make mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each of 54.55% is not good.

2) Student errors in modeling situations, amounting to 60.61%, are sufficient, and student errors in making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting successively 50%, 50%, 50% are not good. In detail, for the first problem, errors students in making situation models, making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each of 63.64%, means that it is classified as sufficient. The second problem, student errors in creating situation models of 72.73% are relatively good. Students' errors in making mathematical models, solving and interpreting each amounted to 40.91% which was classified as very not good. The third problem, student errors in modeling situations, making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting each of 45.45%, means that it is sufficient.

3) Errors made by students tend to be in creating situation models. Students do not understand the description of problems related to real life. Quantitatively, the number of students who experienced errors in modeling situations was 63.64% for the concept of division with remainder, 72.73% for the concept of addition and subtraction, and 45.45% for the concept of multiplication.

4) Errors in making mathematical models, solving, and interpreting are caused by students not understanding the problem or not being able to construct a situation model.

Based on the conclusions above, it is recommended for teachers to more intensively relate mathematics to real life. Students need to be exposed to more real life problems in order to see the relationship between mathematics and real life and students are more motivated to learn mathematics.

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